

Women Investors' Perception Towards Investment in Mutual Funds

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Rekha, M., and N. NandhiniPriya. "Women Investors' Perception Towards Investment in Mutual Funds." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 116–22.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3412522>

Mrs.M.Rekha, M.Com., M.Phil.,

Assistant Professor

Department of M.Com (Accounting and Finance)

SDNB Vaishnav College for Women, Chennai

N.NandhiniPriya

II M.Com (Accounting and Finance)

SDNB Vaishnav College for Women, Chennai

Abstract

A Mutual Fund is one of the most expedient investment options for the common man in India as it provides an opportunity to invest in a broad, professionally managed bunch of securities at a relatively low cost. The Mutual Fund industry unfolds as an important segment of the financial market of India as it channelizes and mobilizes funds from several investors and invest the same in the prominent equity and debt instruments. Idle funds are considered dangerous but at the same time investment in an ideal option is essential. This risk is borne by the competent fund manager, which is its best part. This context helps to have knowledge about the various factors influencing the buying behavior of Mutual Fund investors. This study aids to understand the attitude of women investors towards investment in Mutual Funds and further a brief understanding of how Mutual Fund succours for the sustenance of the upward trend of the financial market of India as well as understanding the term 'Green Mutual Funds', its importance for the longevity of the environment we dwell in.

Keywords: Mutual Funds, Women Investors' Attitude and Perception, Sustainable Development.

Introduction

Mutual Funds are financial intermediaries that collect funds from various small investors (Unit holders) and invest the same in large investment avenues on behalf of the investors and issue them securities (units). They serve as pure intermediary between small investors and the vast financial market. Mutual Funds involve three cardinal parties viz Sponsor, the Trust and the Asset Management Company (AMC). In short, Mutual Fund has large number of investors with one common objective through which the income that is generated is then distributed proportionately amongst all investors.

Organisation of Mutual Funds

Mutual Funds involve three cardinal parties viz Sponsor, the Trust and the Asset Management Company (AMC). The one

who promotes Mutual Funds is the Sponsor who appoints the Trust which in turn hires Asset Management Company (AMC). AMC involves professional managers who conduct research as they take responsibility to invest the savings of the small investors in an optimum portfolio.

Review of Literature

Desigan et al. (2006) analysed the investment behaviour of women in Mutual Funds and has revealed that lack of knowledge and hesitation due to risk involved caused them to rely on other investment options but due to change in time women start to prefer Mutual Funds which seem to have a growing pace in the mere future.

T. T. Vasanthakumari et al. (2007) revealed how awareness plays a pivotal role in pooling funds for Mutual Funds and the perception of investors towards investment in these Funds which seem to be different once investors have a clear study of the concept of Mutual Funds.

Rajesh Kumar and R.S.Arora (2013) analyzed on Investor’s perception about Mutual Funds in India which helped to understand few important aspects that influenced the investors towards their investment in Fund units.

Rajdeep Kumar Raut and Niladri Das (2015) demonstrated the behaviour of investors towards decision making process as to how important it is to make correct decision with correct guidance when it comes to huge investment.

T. Velumurugan and N. Vijay Anand (2015) examined the various factors which influence the mutual fund investment decision making using Regression analysis.

S. Neelima and Dr. D. Surya Chandra Rao (2016) has implied factor analysis to study the factors influencing the investors investing in mutual funds and various schemes of the investment avenue where the study is considered useful for the Asset Management Company for understanding the investor’s buying behaviour.

Varun Sagar Singal and Dr.Rishi Manrai (2018) identified factors that prevent the investors from investing in Mutual Funds and the ways through which the Companies can improve the same to invite many investors.

Objectives

- To identify the various factors influencing the buying behaviour of Mutual Fund investors.
- To understand the attitude of women investors towards investment in Mutual Funds.
- To develop knowledge of Green Mutual Funds and its increasing importance in the financial market.

Factors Influencing the Buying Behaviour of Mutual Fund Investors

The Unit holders (at retail level) are highly heterogeneous group who expect to gain regular return with low risk. There is immense competition among the Asset Management Companies to sustain in the financial market for which they need to understand the changing buying behaviour of these investors. There is always a set of factors which will influence the investors in their buying behaviour as identified by T.Velmurugan and N.Vijai Anand (2015) because being rational, the investors tend to earn well by changing their investment pattern based on their requirements which are listed below:

Past Performance of the Units	Date of Inception
Current situation of the market	Awareness before investing

Dividend history	Rating by rating agency of funds
Diversification of risk	Fund Type and size
Liquidity options	Reputation of Fund Manager
Redemption facilities	Investor's grievance and redressal facilities
Professional guidance	Fund Sustainability

Analysis of the Factors Influencing Buying Behaviour of Mutual Fund Investors

T. Velumurugan and N.Vijay Anand (2015) analysed that the dependent variable being “Mutual Fund Investment” was influenced by independent variables which were divided into relatively influencing variables and not relatively influencing variables.

- Fund Type and Fund Size, Reputation of Fund Manager, Past performance of units in the market and Dividend history had a relative influence on the dependent variable. For instance for every unit increase in fund size and past performance, the mutual fund investment will go up as per the analysis.
- Current situation of market, Liquidity option, Redemption facility, Rating by rating agency, Fund Sustainability and Investor's grievance and redressal facilities had a non relative influence on the dependent variable.

The researcher concluded that a new investor will be influenced and will intend to know the influence of the above said factors before investing in Mutual Funds in order to get high return with low risks.

Analysis of Other Factors

There are various other factors which may influence the investors towards investment in Mutual Funds and they are Risk involved, Diversification of risk, Professional guidance, Date of Inception, Awareness before investing which are explained below:

Date of Inception

Inception date is the date on which the fund has been launched. This is the effective date from which the fund starts to operate. Funds with long track records help the investors to assess the overall performance of the funds.

Professional Guidance

Buy low and sell high is that being expected by majority of investors. In order to achieve this, deep understanding of the transaction in funds is essential which will involve expertise in the field, time consumption. Hence this can be sorted with proper professional guidance.

Diversification of Risk

Business is always prone to risk which is the same in case of Mutual Funds too. But proper analysis will reduce the risk involved in the investment made. Hence this can be done with the support of fund managers who help in diversification of risk.

Attitude of Women Investors Towards Investment in Mutual Funds

Women have turned to be breadwinners of their families in the recent times. As they started earning, they give more importance for savings in order to support their retirement life. Women normally tend to take less risk in terms of long term investments. Considering this mutual funds seem to cover every aspect of their satisfaction only through proper assistance. Hence if attitude of women investors are to be considered, the following points seem to be convincing.

Parking Funds in Highly Secure Avenues

Women tend to invest surplus funds in those options which are always secure. They opt for minimum risk investment avenues. Hence safety plays a major aspect when it comes to investment.

Preference Towards Option Which Fetches Expected Return

Investment is made with an intention to earn a return. Hence those schemes which offer a good amount of return is given priority when it comes to attitude of women investors towards investment in mutual funds.

Updation Through Constant Assistance

The special feature of Mutual Fund is the assistance provided by the Fund Managers. Hence based on the changing requirement of the investors the fund managers need to extend their support for which constant updation is essential.

Most Suitable for Small Investments

Mutual Funds invites small investors in large numbers to mobilize and channelise funds in the optimum investment avenue.

Green Mutual Funds

Mutual Funds that invest in Green initiatives is referred to as Green Mutual Funds. Green initiatives include investment in those companies which are engaged in socially and environmentally supportive businesses using sustainable means such as solar, wind, bio fuels and geothermal technology. Investors tend to invest in these type of funds as concern towards these initiatives are increasing in their minds in the recent times thus promoting sustainable development.

Importance of Green Mutual Funds

Green Mutual Funds are important as

- It is typically rewarding both the investor and the community
- The socially responsible company's reputation reaches a remarkable height in the financial market
- This concept aims at better workplace, concern for its products, consumers and the environment thus striving hard for a better future.

Green Funds in India

- Canara Robeco Mutual Fund in tie up with Switzerland based 'Sustainable Asset Management(SAM) has launched platform to invest in projects concerning water, to efficiently consume energy resources and climate changes.
- UTI Ventures has invested in Pesco Beam Environmental Solutions, a firm which is involved in waste oil recycling and in alternate energy system.
- Canara Bank has invested in Natura Fibretech which finds an alternative for timber used in Construction sector.

Development in Green Mutual Funds

In India there is increasing concern for sustainability. Hence this concept has entered the financial market as well and has induced numerous companies to invest in those green projects which in turn has interested majority of general public to invest in these ventures and one such example has been briefed below:

Quantum Mutual Fund – Esg Equity Fund

Quantum Mutual Fund has launched ESG Equity Fund which will primarily invest in Indian Companies. This initiative has been taken to give importance to Environment, Social and Governance (ESG) Funds. Chirag Mehta – Senior Fund Manager – Alternative Investments, Sneha Joshi – Associate Fund Manager – Alternative Investments are jointly responsible for this new initiative.

Investment Strategy

Investment in stocks of Indian Companies will be made after intensively analysing the environment, social and governance standards/practices. The fund house intends to recognise and invest in clean and green equity funds. They also consider those companies which foresee the climatic changes and issues in the society and devise and equip themselves will sustain in the long run even during the period of downturn. Further they extend to follow “ESG Framework” to intensively understand the company’s management practices, handling risk and sustainability of the business. In this way they intend to help investors to park their surplus funds in sustainable long term growth prospects.

Conclusions and Implications

Savings aspect in the minds of women investors is to be encouraged and the small units are to be mobilized for investment in the appropriate investment option. Normally women tend to concentrate on savings in a higher sense when compared to men. Hence this has to be brought to the notice of women to make them aware of the connectivity between period of investment and the risk-return part of any investment option to make them take the right choice.

There is always a scope for further study on Green Mutual Funds as it is the emerging investment avenue for those encouraging sustainability. In addition to this we would like to suggest few important implications to the Government such as to minimize the lock in period of investment, provide tax benefits for those invested in green projects thus encouraging numerous others to invest in those projects and ultimately to create awareness to investors to channelise their funds in Mutual Funds Schemes.

References

1. Agarwal, G.D., (1992), “Mutual Funds and Investors Interest”, Chartered Secretary, Vol. 22, No.1, 23-24.
2. Bajtelsmit, V. L., &Bernasek, A. (1996) “Why Do Women Invest Differently than Men?” Financial Counselling and Planning, 7.
3. Shanmugham, R., (2000), “Factors Influencing Investment Decisions”, Indian Capital Markets – Trends and Dimensions (ed.), Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi, 2000.
4. Ramamoorthy.V.E and Rajeshwari.T.R (2001), Mutual Fund and Self-Regulation in Indian Context, Sankalpa, Volume. IX, July -December, pp.95-101.
5. Raman T P, “Mutual Funds: Focus on Retail Investor”, THE HINDU Survey of Indian Industry (2003), pp. 75-76.

6. Ranganathan (2004), Study Of Fund Selection Behaviour of Individual Investors Towards Mutual Funds – With Reference to Mumbai City, M. Phil Thesis in Commerce, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai.
7. C. Gnana Desigan, S. Kalaiselvi, L. Anusuya (2006) “Women Investor’s Perception Towards Investment: An Empirical Study” Indian Journal of Marketing, Volume36, Issue 4, April 2006.
8. T. Devasenathipathi, Dr. P.T.Saleendran and Dr. A. Shanmugasundram (2007) “Awareness and perception of people Towards Mutual Funds at Coimbatore City” Indian Journal of Finance, Volume 1, Issue 4, October – November 2007.
9. Martenson. R. (2008). Are men better investors than women? Gender differences in mutual fund and pension investments. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing* , 13, 72-81.
10. Vijayalaxmi. R., & Jayasathya. R. (2009, January-March). A Study on the Factors Influencing The Selection of Mutual Fund Company. *Journal Of Contemporary Research In Management*, 145-153.
11. N Walia, R Kiran (2009), An analysis of investor’s risk perception towards mutual funds services, *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(5), 2009.
12. Singh BK, Jha AK (2009), An empirical study on awareness & acceptability of mutual fund, *Regional Student’s Conference, ICWAI, 2009*, 49-55.
13. G.V.Satya Sekhar (2011) “Green Funds and Green Investing: A New Route to Green India” *SSRN Electronic Journal*, June 2011.
14. P. Alekhya (2012), “A Study on Performance Evaluation of Public & Private Sector Mutual Funds in India”, *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing & Management Review*, Vol. 1, No. 2, October 2012.
15. Dr. Binod Kumar Singh (2012) “ A Study on Investor’s attitude towards Mutual Funds as an Investment Option”, *International Journal of Research in Management*, Volume 2, Issue 2, March 2012.
16. Mehta, S., & Shah, C. (2012)”Preference of Investors for Indian Mutual Funds and itsPerformance Evaluation” *Pacific Business Review International*, 5 (3), 62-76.
17. Rajesh Kumar and R.S. Arora (2013) “Investor’s Perception About Mutual Funds In India: An Empirical Study” *Indian Journal of Finance*, Volume 7, Issue No.1, January 2013, PP 44-52.
18. Sellappan. R, Jamuna, S & Kavitha, T. (2013) “Investment Attitude of Women towards different sources of Securities- A Factor Analysis Approach”, *Global Journal Of Management and Business Research Finance*, 13 (3).
19. Sharma, R., &Pandya, N. (2013) “Investing in Mutual Fund: An Overview”, *Asian Research Journal of Business Management* , 1 (1), 44-57.
20. Sanjay Kaushik, Gareema Kamboj, Diksha kakkar (2013) “Trade-offs between Investor’s Perceptions of Risk, Return, Service Quality and Mutual Fund Investments”, *Indian Journal of Finance*, Volume 7, Issue 12, December 2013.
21. Prabhavathi, Y & Kishore, N. T. (2013)”Investors preference towards Mutual Fund and Future Investments: A Case study of India”, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3 (11).
22. V Rathnamani (2013), Investor’s Preferences towards Mutual Fund Industry in Trichy, *Journal of Business and Management*, 6, 2013, 48-55.
23. C Sundar, S Prakash (2014), Quantitative Analysis of Indian Mutual Funds: Equity Schemes, *Indian Journal of Finance*, 8, 2014, 20-32.
24. P. Paramashivaiah, Puttaswamy, Ramya S.K., (2014) “Changing Risk Perception of Women Investors: An Emperical Study”, *Indian Journal of Finance*, Volume 8, Issue No. 6, June 2014.

25. Suman Chakraborty, Sabat Kumar Digal (2015) “Empirical Evidence of household savings objectives: A Demographic Comparison”, Indian Journal of Finance, Volume 9, Issue 10, October 2015.
26. Rajdeep Kumar Raut and Niladri Das (2015) “Behavioural Prospects of Individual Investor Decision Making Process: A Review” Indian Journal of Finance, Volume 9, Issue 4, July 2015.
27. T. Velmurugan and N. Vijai Anand (2015) “A Study on Factor Influencing Mutual Fund Investment - Special Reference to Investor in Pharmaceutical Sector at Chennai Metro City” International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research, ISSN 0976 – 044X, September – October 2015; Article No. 34, Pages: 214-219.
28. S. Neelima & Dr. D. Surya Chandra Rao (2016) “Factors Influencing Investors In Mutual Funds Selection” IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM) e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668. Volume 18, Issue 7 .Ver. IV, PP 41-49.
29. Prafulla Kumar Swain, Manoranjan Dash (2017) “A Literature review on Investor’s perception towards Mutual Funds with reference to performance, risk-return and awareness”, Indian Journal of Finance, Volume 11, Issue No.12, December 2017.
30. Varun Sagar Singal and Dr. Rishi Manrai (2018), “Factors Affecting Investment in Mutual Funds” Journal of General Management Research, Vol. 5, Issue 2, July 2018, pp. 96–107.
31. www.economicstime.com.
32. www.mutualfundssahihai.com.